

LEGAL FOUNDATIONS FOR ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN LOCAL GOVERNMENT AUTHORITIES

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Annotation: This article analyzes the legal foundations, unique aspects, and some issues regarding the assessment of the effectiveness of civil servants in local government administrations. It also examines the opinions and remarks of local and foreign scholars.

Keywords: local government authorities, civil servant, effectiveness assessment, legal foundations.

Currently, one of the main processes in the local government system is evaluating the effectiveness and efficiency of civil servants' activities. In his address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 28, 2018, President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev stated, "We must recognize a simple truth today. There is a lack of highly qualified and competent personnel in state agencies. So far, the status of civil servants has not been defined, and transparent mechanisms for recruitment into civil service have not been developed. To solve these issues, it is essential to establish an effective system for impartial assessment of civil servants' activities!" .

Certainly, assessing the effectiveness of civil service is essential for both government agencies and society. This type of assessment allows society to monitor the quality of activities within state institutions .

Currently, the KPI (Key Performance Indicator) system is widely used in evaluating effectiveness globally. In practice, this involves overall assessments of organizational performance, evaluations of leadership, and assessments of all employees' effectiveness.

A significant aspect of this KPI system is that key performance indicators are developed based on the primary responsibilities of district (city) deputy mayors, and their achievement is evaluated quarterly using a scoring system.

Since 2021, the Agency for the Development of Civil Service has implemented a rating system for all regional, district, and city governors and their deputies based on performance indicators (EMSK, KPI). The rating is divided into six categories: high-performing regions; best region; worst region; deputy rankings; top 20 districts; and bottom 20 districts .

In assessing the activities of district (city) governors and their deputies, several key aspects of the effectiveness assessment system based on the most important performance indicators can be highlighted:

First, each deputy governor plans the execution of their most important tasks in advance.

Second, to protect the rights of deputy governors, they are incentivized or held accountable based on their achievement of established performance indicators.

Third, deputy governors are relieved of excessive tasks and assignments that fall outside their authority.

Fourth, the assessment of governors and their deputies allows for public oversight.

Article 36 of the Law on Civil Service stipulates the establishment of a system for evaluating the effectiveness of civil servants based on the most important indicators to ensure fair and impartial criteria for promotion in service. This includes that the methodology for assessing the effectiveness of civil servants is determined by a specially authorized state body, which considers the specific characteristics of the activities of civil servants when setting internal procedures.

Additionally, on March 13, 2024, the President of Uzbekistan issued Decree No. UP-49 on "Measures to Improve the System for Assessing the Effectiveness of Republic and Local Executive Authorities and Economic Associations ." This decree establishes the procedures for implementing its norms. On July 31, 2024, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Decision No. 463 on "Measures to Organize the Assessment of the Activities of Leaders and Their Deputies of Republic and Local Executive Authorities Based on Key Performance Indicators ."

With this decision, the regulations for assessing the activities of deputies of local executive authorities based on key performance indicators were approved.

According to this regulation:

- The key performance indicators for the activities of deputies of local executive authorities will reflect the targeted indicators defined within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, as well as the tasks and directives assigned by the President of Uzbekistan and the Cabinet of Ministers to the respective executive authorities.

Based on the key performance indicators of the activities of the leaders and their deputies of the Republic and local executive authorities and economic associations, the following procedures are established:

- The effectiveness indicators for the next year for the deputies of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the deputies of the governors of regions and Tashkent city will be approved by the Cabinet of Ministers.
- Based on the effectiveness indicators of the deputies of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and the deputies of the governors of regions and Tashkent city, the effectiveness indicators for the deputies of district (city) governors will be approved by the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the governors of the regions, and the mayor of Tashkent.
- Information on the achievement of effectiveness indicators will be generated automatically or through confirmation.
- Information regarding the achievement of effectiveness indicators will be entered into the "samardorlik.uz" electronic platform by the deputies of local executive authority leaders and confirmed by responsible persons designated by the Cabinet of Ministers, leading to the formation of a ranking of evaluated leaders.

The adoption of the above decree and decision creates opportunities for a professional approach to public administration, strengthens results-oriented effective management, and attracts qualified personnel. Additionally, it enhances the accountability of leadership by fostering a culture of assessing the effectiveness of their activities .

Currently, the effectiveness of the deputies of district (city) governors in the Republic of Karakalpakstan is evaluated in seven areas on the "samardorlik.uz" electronic platform. The annual activities are divided into four quarters, with performance indicators developed based on the duties of the deputy governors. The relevant ministries input data on the achievement of these indicators into the platform, and rankings are generated based on the results, which are then used to consider incentives or disciplinary measures.

For example, in the annex to Decision No. 277-13-0-D/22 of the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Karakalpakstan dated May 17, 2022, the activities of the deputy governor for agriculture and water management are assessed based on seven key performance indicators. The results are categorized into four tiers: excellent (≤ 100 points), good (≤ 90 points), satisfactory (≤ 70 points), and unsatisfactory (> 70 points).

In conclusion, it is important to note that the establishment of a fair assessment system for the effectiveness of civil servants in local government is crucial for shaping public servants who serve the people.

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